

AN APPLICATION OF INVENTORY MODEL BASED ON TRANSSHIPMENT TO A DISASTER RELIEF SECTOR

Dr. S. Balamohan* & N. Karthika**

* Principal, SSM College of Engineering, Komarapalayam, Tamilnadu

** Research Scholar in Mathematics, Bharathiyar University, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. S. Balamohan & N. Karthika, "An Application of Inventory Model Based on Transshipment to a Disaster Relief Sector", International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Page Number 18-21, Volume 1,

Issue 2, 2016.

Abstract:

In a disaster relief system transshipment plays an important role to improve the management of inventory. For a humanitarian supply chain with transshipment and without transshipment the system dynamics simulation was used to compare inventory control and costs. The simulation study on a system consisting of two warehouses where transshipment is allowed compared to the alternative where transshipment is not allowed, gives the framework. The literature studies indicate that transshipment may reduce costs and improve service levels. The same is also used in disaster relief system based on inventory levels maintained in the warehouses. In case transshipment may be more expensive, this assumes the cost of replenishing inventory as a result of emergency purchase cost.

Key Words: Transshipment, Disaster Relief, Humanitarian Supply Chain, System Dynamics & Simulation

Introduction:

Natural disaster cannot be predicted with accuracy earlier so it is hard to forecast the demand, but it is essential for recovery of the affected areas. Uncertainties of the disasters themselves such as location, timing, degree of severity and lack of financial and personal resources makes it very difficult to match the demands caused by the disaster to the supply needed in a timely manner for relief activities. So purchasing plan cannot be made before, but must be fulfilled after it happens. Storage of enough resources before a disaster in a strategic location, with the help of transshipment can help after disaster. The basic needs of human, such as food, clothing, personal and medicine delivery to the affected areas requires a tremendous coordination which leads to resources scarcity or oversupply. So the right amount of supplies to the right place is important. There are many successful inventory models for commercial supply chain exists, but the supply chain for disaster relief requires a different model. The inventory policies for both pre disaster and post disaster was used and transshipment will be employed to determine how and where to store before a disaster and how and where to transship after disaster. And finally the emergency supply chain with simulation analysis is produced to the relief supply chain.

Background Information:

After a disaster an emergency relief chain may include many flows, and actors. Considering the eleven scenarios of commercial supply chain, such as electronic point of sales, vendor managed inventory, e-shopping, emergency transshipment, lead times, disposal ratio, time to adjust inventory, unit cost(UC) of emergency purchase, UC of pre purchase, UC of disposal, UC of transshipment (Pedro Reyes 2013). And the actors are international relief organization, local relief organization, local government, donors, private sector companies and militaries. Inventory systems often account for a large proportion of a business costs. This makes it crucial to manage them efficiently. The traditional design of an inventory system is hierarchal, with transportation flows from one echelon to the next, which is from manufacturers to wholesalers and from wholesalers to retailers. More flexible system also allows lateral transshipment within an echelon. In this way, members of the same echelon pool their inventories, which can allow them to lower inventory levels and costs whilst still achieving the required service levels. Lateral transshipments can be divided into emergency lateral transshipments (ELTs), preventive lateral transshipments (PLTs), and service level adjustments (SLAs). ELT mandates emergency redistribution from a retailer with ample stock to a retailer that has reached a stock out. PLT reduces this risk by redistributing stock to prevent a stock out at a retailer before demand exceeds the inventory level. In other words, ELT responds to actual stock outs while PLT reduces the risk of possible future stock outs. The SLA policy combines the ELT and PLT policies together to reduce the risk of stock outs in advance and efficiently respond to actual stock outs. In this paper, we give a complete overview on how PLT, ELT and SLA policies play an important role in improving service levels and reducing inventory cost.

Emergency Transshipment System:

There are four sub systems in the framework, called purchase, inventory, distribution, and information technology and knowledge discovery. In this paper, we assume that the lead time of transshipment between warehouses is always shorter than the total time of purchase lead time and order fulfill time from suppliers. Therefore, besides these four sub systems, we define a new system called emergency transshipment. Using the information technology and knowledge discovery (IT & KD) system, we can input affected area information and output reliable relief plans, such as how to get the relief supplies, by transshipment or purchasing, purchase natively or globally. If our relief plan is to purchase, then we go to purchase system, or else we go to the

inventory system to judge if the storages in local warehouse are enough or if transshipments are necessary, and how to choose the suppliers? In order to meet the transshipment requirements and facilitate rapid shipping between warehouses, advanced information systems must be in place to allow actors to know what other actors have in stock. The purchase system includes two sub systems called pre-purchase and emergency purchase. The operation characters of pre-purchase are the same as that of commercial purchase. Emergency purchase is totally different from pre-purchase, not only in its purchase time and purchase quantity, but also in the probable inaccessibility of demand points. The suppliers must be prepared to produce adequate materials for relief and ship them immediately anywhere at any time, which is impossible. We suppose that the frequency of disasters is not known but the maximum demand can be deduced based on the local disaster records and other similar cases via knowledge discovery technology. As a result, the inventory policy is to trace a constant which can minimize the total cost. Higher inventory will make relief easier, however too much inventory will lead to high purchase and inventory holding costs. But lower inventory can cause higher risk, if emergency purchasing is inefficient. Besides the time cost, inventory policies of relief materials are affected by many factors such as cost to produce, transport and store relief material. Various effects of these factors can be transferred mathematically into a parameter, regarded as cost in this work. The warehouses must cooperate to fulfill the demand when an emergency occurs; we prefer a centralized distribution strategy. Centralized distribution can even lead to global optimization in commercial supply chains when a network is owned by a single entity or a centralized system that includes many organizations. In relief supply systems, besides cooperation among warehouses owned by one distribution center, distribution systems must cooperate with other systems. For example, a distribution system must cooperate with an inventory system to judge the optimal transport and storage quantities. Also, the time cost of distribution and delivery is very important to the decision of transshipment and purchase systems. Transportation optimization of a disaster relief plan is more complex than that of commercial logistics because of the possible absence of an information route condition and other resources. That is, a distribution system depends most on the IT & KD system. The transshipment planning system is rather complex for the decision variables are outputs of other sub systems and at the same time the outputs of it will affect the decisions of other sub systems. Considering this kind of interaction, using a traditional mathematic model such as stochastic mixed integer program to describe this transshipment system and try to get the optimized policy is impossible.

Inventory Structure for Single Warehouse with Transshipment:

Assume there is one distribution center with many warehouses. Warehouses are denoted as inventory i, j, k... First, we will model one warehouse, inventory i. The local inventory i has two resources, pre-purchase from distribution center and post-transshipment from local inventory k. In case of the uncertainty of relief demand, we must purchase goods and store them as inventories beforehand, we call this pre-purchase. The basic purchase policy is if the disaster happened and the local warehouse, inventory i is not destroyed, the relief demands can be fulfilled by inventory i. The pre-purchase of inventory i is based on the potential demand and prediction of damages. If the disaster happened and the local warehouse i an Inventory k destroyed, the relief demands must be fulfilled by transshipments. We assume that at least one warehouse will fulfill the relief demand, in our model marked as inventory k. Of course, if the disaster does not happen locally, then inventory i can be used to fulfill the relief demand of other areas, such as inventory j whose local inventory is totally destroyed. If no disasters happen before the expiration date of materials, we must redistribute them or dispose of them, which will lead to re-transport and other costs.

Inventory Policy for Single Warehouse with Transshipment:

We use the following parameters:

- P_i =probability of region i being destroyed
- q_i =probability of inventory i being destroyed and inaccessible
- $t_i p$ =probability of condition t of region i, where t=1, 2, 3, 4
- x_i =inventory of region i
- D =real demand of region i
- C_{pi} =unit pre-purchase and storage cost of inventory i
- C_{di} =unit disposal cost of inventory i
- C_{ki} =unit transshipment cost from k to i
- $P_{ii} = p_i(1-q_i)$ =real demand of region i

Condition 1: Region i being destroyed and inventory i is accessible. Probability of this condition is $P_{ii} = p_i(1-q_i)$ Under this condition, there will be relief demand in region i and this demand can be fulfilled by inventory i. The total cost of this condition is as follows: $C_{1i} = c_{pi}d_i + c_{di}(x_i-d_i)$

If the real demand D_i is less than inventory x_i , the storage not used must be redistributed to commercial supply chain or disposed of. In this paper, we call this disposal cost, which indeed varies for various goods and warehouses. But we will define disposal costs to include the cost of purchase, storage, retransmitted, and disposal.

Condition 2: Region i being destroyed and inventory i is inaccessible. Probability of this condition is $p_{2i} = p_iq_i$

Under this condition, there will be relief demand in region i and this demand must be fulfilled by transshipment from other regions, inventory k. The total cost of this condition is $C_{2i} = c_{pi}x_i + c_{tki}d_i$

Condition 3: Region i being safe but Region j being destroyed and inventory j is inaccessible. Probability of this condition is $p_{3i} = (1-p_i) p_i q_i$

Under this condition, there will be relief demand in region j and this demand can be fulfilled by inventory i. The total cost of i is only the pre-purchase and storage cost c_i , just the same as condition 1. Of course there is transshipment cost from i to j, but it belongs to inventory j.

$$C_{3i} = c_{pi}d_i + c_{di}(x_i - d_i)$$

Condition 4: Region i being safe and other inventory j is accessible. Probability of this condition is

$$P_{4i} = (1-p_i) (1-p_i q_i)$$

Under this condition, there will not be relief demand in any region. The storage must be redistributed to commercial supply chain or disposed. The total cost is: $C_{4i} = c_{di}x_i$

Now comes the total cost of inventory i , $c_i = \sum_{i=1}^4 p_{ti}C_{ti}$ [1]

in equation [1], total cost depends on many variables: the possibility of disaster and possibility of warehouse corruption; unit cost of purchase, storage, disposal, transshipment, redistribution; inventory holdings and real disaster relief demand. It is impossible to get the optimal solution and minimize the cost. Furthermore, in relief supply management, we pay more attention to the fulfillment of demand. Therefore, we will simulate our model using system dynamics and discuss the sensitivity of the system.

Simulation and Analysis:

Consider there are three probabilities of disaster and three inventory policies in our simulation, called high, medium and low. Different probabilities of disaster are shown in Figure. In this example, inventory equals 100, 200, and 400.

Simulation Without Transshipment:

If Transshipment demand $j=0$ Then Emergency purchase $i =$ transshipment demand I When demand is low, a different inventory policy can lead to a different total cost. By using computerized simulation, if the relief demand is high, medium or low, the desired inventory should be high to avoid the high emergency purchase cost. At the same time, high desired inventory can lead to high disposal and redistribution costs. In fact, because of the uncertainty of disaster frequency and in order maintain efficiency of relief, we prefer to keep a high inventory which will lead to high costs and waste of recourses, especially when relief demand is low.

Simulation With Transshipment:

Based on different disaster frequencies, simulations are divided into nine groups, Character of Disaster frequency are FLL, FLM, FLH, FML, FMM, FMH, FHL, FHM, FHH In every group, we simulate six inventory policies, Different inventory policies are ILL, IML, IMM, IHL, IHM, IHH.

Total Cost of Different Inventory Policies with Transshipment and Without Transshipment:

By computerized analysis about nine disaster frequencies with six inventory policies in simulation basis method we found the best inventory policies under disaster frequencies are presented as: FLL- ILL, IML, and IMM. FLM- IMM. FLH- IMM. FML- IMM. FMM- IMM. FMH- IMM, IHL, IHM, IHH. FHL- IML, IMM, IHL, IHM. FHM- IMM, IHL, IHM. FHH- IMM, IHL, IHM, IHH.

Table 1: Total Cost structure with and without transshipment						
Simulation						
	Transshipment strategy					
	CW _o T	CWT	EPW _o T	PPCWT	PPCW _o T	TCWT
1_1	383703.4	383272.2	382912.8	383233.9	383138.3	383091.1
1_2	387890	386974.6	386265.4	386935.9	386750.6	386619.7
1_3	387692.4	386820.5	386184.3	386781.8	386535.1	386453
1_4	459879.6	450107.2	441261.2	450062.2	445403.6	445148.4
1_5	401032.2	401716.4	403068.3	401576.2	401767.2	401829.5

2_1	398556.5	398305.7	398140.1	398265.9	398231.7	398207.7
2_2	401881.5	401326.4	401002.7	401286.2	401237.2	401229.8
2_3	401851.6	401410.3	401114.2	401370.1	401345.5	401308.9
2_4	437221.2	432458	429965	432414.8	431441.7	430907.8
2_5	407076.9	407416.6	408026.3	407375.8	407701.7	407923
3_1	387032.6	386667.8	386447.5	386589.1	386556.2	386474.8
3_2	388867.3	388362.8	388728.4	388615.4	388419.6	388419.6
3_3	390015.1	389540.8	389008.2	389421.8	389239.4	389166.7
3_4	450903.1	445015.4	438894	443370.9	442529	440130.9
3_5	401097.4	401171.3	402263.5	401131.2	401528.7	401934
4_1	390474.9	388593.1	387690.8	388554.2	388496.3	388370.7
4_2	399418.2	395888	393491.3	395848.4	395520.6	395436.7
4_3	400056.6	397039.6	394619.1	396999.9	396599.8	396140.6
4_4	567653.4	535974.4	508950.1	535920.8	524879.3	521369.7
4_5	424469	432574.4	433438.8	428531.8	429067.8	431219.8

(CWoT-cost without transshipment, CWT-cost with transshipment, EPWoT- Emergency purchase without transshipment, PPCWoT- Pre-purchase cost without transshipment, PPCWT-prepurchase cost with transshipment, TCWT – Transshipment cost with transshipment). We notice that when inventory policies are the same (medium), the pre-purchase cost with transshipment (line 4) is higher than that of without transshipment (line 5). The reason is that, in order to fulfill the transshipment demand of inventory j, inventory i must purchase more after relief to j. As a result, transshipment is available only when the unit emergency purchase cost of i is higher than the unit pre-purchase cost of i and unit transshipment cost of j.

Conclusion:

This research gives a disaster relief system based on transshipment which proved to be efficient via our simulation example. In our simulation, we only discussed a transshipment system with two warehouses whose unit costs are the same. We assumed that the probable frequency of a disaster is unknown but the maximum demand is known as a constant if the disaster happened. Of course the decision makers can describe the demand and character of different warehouses in detail if they have enough data. This is important for warehouse managers to understand in order to minimize costs and be aware of the ability to provide relief when needed. But, if inventory levels are too low, then emergency purchasing is high resulting in increased cost and possible delayed relief to those in need. In all cases, the key to reducing costs and providing the best care for disaster victims is the information technology and knowledge discovery subsystem. The accuracy of information allows for the output of reliable relief plans in order to get relief supplies to victims by transshipment or purchasing where purchasing is native (local/regional) or global. If our relief plan is to purchase, then managers can go to purchase system, or else to the inventory system to judge if the inventory in the local warehouse is enough or if transshipments are necessary, and how to choose the suppliers. The transshipment requirements can be met only with advanced information systems/technology, which allow managers/relief supervisors to see what other managers/relief supervisors have in stock and facilitate rapid shipping between warehouses. Knowledge discovery is key to the process. Future research will examine more complex systems for disaster relief, allowing for more variability in the system. This research is a first step in determining how best to help improve humanitarian efforts to save lives and help relief organizations and benevolent organizations provide relief when needed.

References:

1. Axsäter, S. (1990b). "Simple solution procedures for a class of two-echelon inventory problems." *Operations Research*, 38 64-69.
2. Axsäter, S. (2006). "A simple procedure for determining order quantities under a fill rate constraint and normally distributed lead-time demand." *European Journal of Operational Research*, 174 (1) 480-491.
3. Balcik, B.; Beamon, B.; Krejci, C.; Muramatsu, K.; And Ramirez, M. (2010). Coordination in humanitarian relief chains: Practices, challenges and opportunities. *International Journal of Production Economics*, v. 126, n. 1, p. 22- 34.
4. EGAN, M. J. (2010). Private goods and services contracts: Increased emergency response capacity or increased vulnerability? *International Journal of Production Economics*, v. 126, n. 1, p. 46-5
5. Lodree, E. J.; Taskin, S. (2009). Supply chain planning for hurricane response with wind speed information updates. *Computers & Operations Research*, v.36, n. 1, p. 2-15
6. Oloruntoba, R. (2010). An analysis of the Cyclone Larry emergency relief chain: Some key success factors. *International Journal of Production Economics*, v. 126, n. 1, p. 85-101.
7. Blakemore, F.P. and Konda, T.F. (2010). "Design-Build Replacement of US-90 Bridge over Bay St. Louis, Mississippi." *Transportation Research Record* 2201, 106-112.